

MENTAL HEALTH OF ADOLESCENTS IN REMOTE AREAS OF NAVOI REGION: THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIO-HYGIENIC FACTORS

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Abstract. The mental health of adolescents in remote areas is one of the most pressing issues in modern public health. The specific socio-hygienic conditions of remote industrial regions form a unique complex of risk factors for adolescent mental development disorders. The aim of the research is to study the state of mental health and psycho-emotional status of adolescents in remote areas of the Navoi region and to establish its relationship with socio-hygienic factors. A cross-sectional epidemiological study was conducted using standardized psychological methods, social and hygienic questionnaires, and statistical analysis. It has been established that adolescents in remote areas of Navoi region are characterized by a higher level of anxiety, reduced cognitive development indicators, and limited resources of psychosocial adaptation compared to regulatory indicators. Priority risk factors are chronic psychosocial stress, limited access to educational resources, and the low level of parental education. Scientifically based recommendations have been developed for the prevention of mental health disorders in adolescents in remote areas.

Keywords: mental health, adolescents, remote areas, Navoi region, socio-hygienic factors, anxiety, cognitive development, prevention.

Introduction. The mental health of adolescents represents one of the priority problems of modern public health. According to WHO data, every fifth teenager in the world has certain mental health disorders, with most of them remaining without proper diagnosis and treatment [1]. Disorders of mental development in adolescence are a significant predictor of decreased work capacity and social maladjustment in adulthood [2].

Social and hygienic living conditions have a significant impact on the mental health of adolescents. Studies in recent years have convincingly shown that adolescents from low-income families living in unfavorable socio-economic conditions have a higher risk of developing anxiety and depressive disorders, cognitive impairments, and social maladjustment [3, 4]. In remote areas, these risks are exacerbated by limited access to psychological assistance, insufficient public awareness of mental health issues, and stigmatization of mental disorders [5].

The Navoi region of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a unique case study for studying the influence of socio-hygienic factors on the mental health of adolescents. The specifics of the region - desert climate, intensive industrial activity, significant remoteness of settlements from the regional center - form a unique complex of factors influencing the psycho-emotional state of adolescents [6]. At the same time, this problem in the context of the Navoi region has not previously been the subject of special scientific research.

The aim of the research is to study the state of mental health and psycho-emotional status of 17-19-year-old adolescents in remote areas of the Navoi region and to establish its relationship with priority socio-hygienic factors.

Materials and methods. Cross-sectional (one-time) epidemiological study based on educational institutions in remote areas of Navoi region.

Period of implementation: 2022-2024. Mental health assessment tools:

- Spielberger-Khanin Anxiety Scale (STAI) - for assessing the level of reactive and personal anxiety;
- Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) - for screening anxiety and depressive disorders;
- Short Mental Status Assessment Scale (MMSE) - for assessing cognitive functions;
- Social adaptation questionnaire - to assess the level of psychosocial adaptation of adolescents.

The socio-hygienic questionnaire included an assessment of the level of chronic psychosocial stress, the availability of educational resources, the level of education of parents, the nature of intra-family relationships, and social support.

Statistical methods. Statistical data processing was carried out using the SPSS Statistics 26.0 package. Descriptive statistics methods, comparative analysis, correlation analysis, multiple logistic regression with calculation of OR and 95% CI were used. Significance level $p < 0.05$.

Results. Analysis of the results of psychological testing revealed that adolescents in remote areas of the Navoi region are characterized by an increased level of personal anxiety. According to the HADS scale, a clinically significant level of anxiety (≥ 8 points) was identified in a significant proportion of the examined adolescents, which significantly exceeds population standards.

The obtained results indicate that adolescents in remote areas of the Navoi region represent an increased risk group for mental health disorders. The identified high level of anxiety and cognitive impairments aligns with research data conducted under similar socio-economic conditions in other regions of the world [9, 10].

The established role of chronic psychosocial stress as a leading risk factor (OR = 3.1) deserves special attention. In the conditions of remote areas of the Navoi region, sources of chronic stress for adolescents are the economic instability of the family, limited prospects for professional self-realization, the impact of industrial environmental factors, and social isolation. These factors form a specific "stress profile" of adolescents in the region, requiring the development of targeted psychoprophylactic programs.

Limited access to educational resources (OR = 2.6) also contributes significantly to the formation of cognitive impairments in adolescents. This aligns with the concept of "educational inequality" as a determinant of health, widely discussed in contemporary public health literature [11].

Conclusion. Adolescents in remote areas of Navoi region are characterized by an increased level of anxiety, decreased cognitive development indicators, and limited resources of psychosocial adaptation. Priority risk factors for mental health disorders are chronic psychosocial stress, limited access to educational resources, and an unfavorable family climate. To improve adolescent mental health indicators, it is necessary to implement a comprehensive interdepartmental program that includes psycho-preventive measures in educational institutions, improving the accessibility of psychological assistance, and working with adolescent families.

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